

THE NECESSITY OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ON SPORTS TERMINOLOGY IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation. The paper emphasizes the importance of scientific research on the structural-grammatical, semantic, derivational, thematic, and lexicographic characteristics of sports terminology in the context of studying the Uzbek national "sport" semantic field as an integral part of contemporary culture. It underscores the significance of analyzing the synchronic state of Uzbek language sports terminology by dividing it into two layers, as well as the semantic classification of sports terminology and the methods for expanding sports vocabulary.

Keywords: sports terminology, semantic categorization, sports lexicon, semantic domain, acquisition stratum, own stratum, sports discourse

Currently, in the field of global linguistics, the examination of matters such as terminology, associated challenges, term and term concept, lexical-semantic characteristics, and structural composition of terms has advanced significantly. In light of this development, the methodologies employed in the creation and selection of terms within contemporary terminology across all languages, their efficacy, adherence to standards, and active utilization of the formulated terms in accordance with the norms of the literary language, as well as the execution of research in contemporary facets pertaining to the lexical layers of the terms, are being prioritized. Consequently, these factors necessitate a scientific investigation of the structural-grammatical, semantic, derivational, thematic, and lexicographic attributes of sports terminology in the discipline of linguistics.

In the field of terminology in Uzbek linguistics, H.A. Jamolkhanov is conducting scientific research on the composition and development of Uzbek botanical terminology. Furthermore, H. Dadaboev conducted research on socio-political and socio-economic terminology, N. Shodmonov on musical terms, Kh. Jabborov on agricultural lexicon, M. Kh. Kasimova on legal terminology of the Uzbek language, Kh. V. Mirzaahmedova on structural layers of Persian transport terms, M. .G. Nematova plant names in Uzbek language, I. Yuldashev Uzbek literary terminology, G. Gulomova legal terminology, R. Doniyorov technical terminology of Uzbek language, O. Ramazonov Uzbek mathematical terminology, M.A. Alieva semantic-grammatical study of gas terms, D.S. Saidkodiroya internet terms, Z.A.Djurabaeva ecological terms, H.Sh. Narkhodjaeva terms meaning process, O.T. Orinova livestock terms, H.E. Yodgorov military terminology, S.Kh. Nurmatova astro-aerospace terminology in English, Russian and Uzbek languages , T.Q. Valiev conducted research on structural-semantic features and lexicographical interpretation of Uzbek language road construction terms [1, 3,5,6,7,].

In the field of Uzbek linguistics, M. Boboyorov emphasized the processes of field terminology development based on the internal capabilities of the Uzbek language and external factors. Z. Abdullaeva examined the influence of historical and social factors on the development of terms. Kh.Sarimsokov studied the history of the formation of sports terms and neologisms in Uzbek and English, methods of creation (lexical-semantic, derivational, etc.), and the terminological properties of phraseological units.[2,3]

In the era of globalization and computerization, the Republic of Uzbekistan's position in the international community has led to the rapid development of interstate economic, political, cultural, and other relations. The positive outcomes of such

relations are evident not only in socio-political and cultural-economic spheres but also in the realm of language.

In the world of sports, Uzbek words such as "kurash (meaning:fight)," "halol (meaning: honest)," "yonbosh (meaning:side)," "chala," "rebuke," "dakki," "ghirrom," "stop," "fight," "bow," "durang," "elka," and "bekor" have gained popularity as terms related to wrestling sports. These terms have enriched the lexical base of Uzbek linguistics to a significant extent.

Examples of Uzbek literature that explore the sport of wrestling include Togay Murad's "Stars will burn forever," Said Ahmed's "Ufq," and O'tkir Hashimov's "Works of the World." These works provide valuable insights into the cultural and historical significance of wrestling in Uzbekistan.

The terminology of the Uzbek national "sport" semantic field has undergone intricate phases of evolution and linguistic alterations due to societal, economic, and political circumstances across various eras. The composition of this field's terminological system has reached its current state over numerous centuries, influenced by the inherent capabilities of the Uzbek language and the distinct impact of other languages.

In this context, the current state of Uzbek sports terminology can be categorized into two distinct strata:

1. The acquisition layer of sports terminology: "hoop", "mace", "gymnastic pommel horse", "gymnastic goat", in swimming: "breaststroke", "synchro", "pool", "crawl", "butterfly"

2. The own layer of sports terminology: "wrestling", "honest", "side", "chala", "rebuke", "dakki", "ghirrom", "stop", "struggle", "bow" in the sport of "wrestling" ", "honest", "side", "time", "draw", "elka", "cancel"

The Uzbek sports terminology can be categorized into four semantic groups:

- 1) Terms describing sports events and actions (50%)
- 2) Terms related to sports and their components (35%)
- 3) Terms indicating professional affiliations (9%)
- 4) Terms highlighting sports qualities, characteristics, and athlete performances (6%)

The enrichment of the sports lexicon in Uzbek languages is achieved through various mechanisms. Firstly, the acquisition of words from other languages contributes to the expansion of the sports vocabulary. Secondly, the loss of certain words from the language also plays a role in shaping the sports lexicon. Thirdly, words undergo semantic changes, including complete shifts in meaning, the emergence of homonyms, and the broadening or narrowing of word meanings. It is important to note that languages are not isolated entities and can influence each other. Consequently, a language may adopt sounds, words, and phrases from another language. Examples of such borrowed terms in the sports lexicon include "referee," "team," "halal" (Arabic), "chala" (Perso-Tajik), "bahodir" (Mongolian), "football," "basketball," "volleyball," "hockey," and "boxing" (which entered English via Russian).

In the realm of sports, terminology often draws upon various languages, resulting in diverse meanings. For instance, "taekwondo" originates from the Korean language, where "tae" signifies foot, "kwon" denotes hand, and "do" represents the path. This martial art emphasizes leg and hand movements. Basketball, derived from the French words "basket" and "ball," is a team sport involving a ball and a basket. The term "chess" has Persian roots, while "volleyball" combines the English word "volley" (hit back) with "ball" to describe a team sport. Boxing, originating from the English word "box," refers to a combat sport involving punching and hitting. Handball, with its German roots ("hand" and "ball"), is a sport played with hands and

a ball. Bodybuilding, also known as "body building," is a sport that focuses on physical development and body structure. Freestyle, a combination of the English words "*free*" and "*style*," is a type of mountain skiing sport that emphasizes individual technique and style.

Wrestling, riding, fencing, shooting, as well as various games and exercises are part of the Uzbek sports terminology. Folk games such as "Oq terakmi, ko`k terak", "Quvlashmachoq", "Qarabtep", "Kopkari" are prime examples of this.

In conclusion, the sports terminology field is constantly evolving, and the growing interest in sports necessitates a more thorough investigation. Lexical compounds often have a slang attribute (e.g., guests, hosts, goalkeeper, goal king), making them popular in sports discourse. Notably, in the speech of sports journalists and commentators, specific elements like slang, which are stylistically neutral and natural, enable the clear expression of emotions in sports. Specialized linguistic tools, particularly slang, form a significant part of the lexical and phraseological sports tools that reflect both the culture described by language and the culture within the language's "lexicographic-phraseological system."

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